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Research Article

UROTHELIAL CARCINOMA; HISTOLOGICAL GRADING AND ASSOCIATION WITH GENDER

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Abstract:

Objective: Objective of this study is to determine frequency of urothelial carcinoma according to histological grading among male and female population

Design and duration: Retrospective study. Duration from January to December 2019

Setting: Study was conducted at Urology department of Bolan University of Medical and Health sciences

Patients and methods: Patients having urinary bladder admitted in urology ward, planned for transurethral resection of bladder tumor, were included in this study using non probability consecutive sampling technique. After transurethral resection of bladder tumor paraffin-embedded and formalin-fixed four micrometer thick sections were prepared for histological examination. All data was documented on a self-made proforma. Means, frequency, standard deviation, percentages and p-value calculated using SPSS software version 24.

Results: Total 110 cases, including 60.9% male and 39.1% female cases were diagnosed with urothelial carcinoma on histopathological examination. Age range of cases was 30-70 years with mean age of 51.4±6.2 years. Maximum patients (38.2%) were between 30-40 years of age.

Conclusion: Urothelial carcinoma is much prevalent among male population but severity of disease is more among female population. No significant association was seen with age.

Key words: Urothelial carcinoma, histological grading, transitional cell carcinoma, gender, age

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INTRODUCTION:

Urothelial carcinoma of urinary bladder is the 4th commonest tumor among males and 9th commonest tumor among females in USA.[1] It is associated with high morbidity and mortality. It contributes 93.4% of all urinary bladder malignancies. [2] In 75%-85% cases it is limited to the mucosa and don't progress further and recurrence rate is high after local resection. [3] Urinary bladder cancers have low prevalence in Sri Lanka while high prevalence in south Asian countries like India (32/million) and Pakistan (89/million). [4-6] Major risk factors of urinary bladder cancer are cigarette smoking and laborers working in musky mines. [7-8] Other risk factors include water pollutants, genetic factor, and male gender, and urinary tract infection, arsenic exposure in environment, consumption of coffee, low socioeconomic status, blood fluke infection in urinary tract, radiation exposure, toxic medicines and cyclophosphamide. There are many factors affecting gender specific outcomes of this carcinoma. [9] Distinct anatomy and change in hormones receptors among females support gender influence on tumor outcome. Moreover other factors include common smoking habit among males, which is a common risk factor of urothelial carcinoma. All those studies reporting males more affected than females also mentioned smoking its commonest risk factor. In this study as well mostly males were smoker. [10] Prognosis of disease is poor among females with high morbidity and mortality than males due to unfavorable pathology. [11] Hormonal and vascularity difference near bladder area may be cause of gender variance of tumor outcomes. According to previous studies prevalence of urinary bladder malignancies have been found more common in postmenopausal women than premenopausal women and aggressive tumors exhibited increased estrogen and androgen receptors. [12]

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

It is a retrospective study of analytical type in which data of patients from previous year 2019 taken from hospital records and on follow-ups. Study duration was one year from January to December 2019 Patients having urinary bladder admitted in urology ward, planned for transurethral resection of bladder tumor, were included in this study using non probability consecutive sampling technique. After transurethral resection of bladder tumor paraffin-embedded and formalin-fixed four micrometer thick sections were prepared for histological examination. All samples were stained with eosin and hematoxylin. Adenocarcinoma, non-invasive papillary urothelial neoplasm, small cell carcinoma and other tumors were excluded from the study. Histologically urothelial carcinoma were graded as low and high grade. Demographic data and information related to disease were documented on a proforma. All data was documented on a self-made proforma. Means, frequency, standard deviation, percentages and p-value calculated using SPSS software version 24. Chi square test was applied. P-value <0.05 was taken as significant.

RESULTS:

Total 110 cases, including 67(60.9%) male and 43(39.1%) female cases were diagnosed with urothelial carcinoma on histopathological examination. Age range of cases was 30-70 years with mean age of 51.4±6.2 years. There were 28.2% cases between 30-40 years, 38.2% between 41-50 years, 22.7% between 51-60 years and 10.9% cases were above 60 years of age. Maximum patients (38.2%) were between 30-40 years of age. There were 81() cases with high grade tumor and 29() were with low grade tumor.

(Table-1) Prevalence of urothelial carcinoma according to age and gender in study group

Age (years)	Number of patients (N)	Male	Female	High grade carcinoma	Low grade carcinoma	P-value
30-40	31	19	12	23	8	0.031
41-50	22	28	14	32	10	0.012
51-60	25	15	10	18	7	0.014
>60	12	5	7	8	4	0.011
Total	110	67	43	81	29	

(Figure-1) Gender wise distribution of urothelial carcinoma in study group

DISCUSSION:

Urothelial carcinoma is a common cancer of urinary bladder arising from environmental carcinogenic effects. It is more common among male population while it is more severe among females. In this study 60.9% male and 39.1% females were affected. Among males and females 70.1% and 79.1% were having high grade carcinoma respectively while low grade carcinoma was detected in 29.9% and 20.9% respectively out of total population of male and female in study group. These results are similar to the study done by Turk H et al, [13] which reported 87.3% males and 12.7% females having urothelial carcinoma. In the past gender relation of this carcinoma has been studied many times. [12-16] There are many factors affecting gender specific outcomes of this carcinoma. Distinct anatomy and change in hormones receptors among females support gender influence on tumor outcome. [18-19] Moreover other factors include common smoking habit among males, which is a common risk factor of urothelial carcinoma. All those studies reporting males more affected than females also mentioned smoking its commonest risk factor. In this study as well mostly males were smoker. In our study high grade carcinoma was common (73.6%) which is similar to the results of a study done by Gupta et al²⁰ which reported high grade carcinoma in 55.3% but results of Koyuncuer et al⁸ were opposite as he reported low grade carcinoma in 68% cases. Many studies show controversial results in this regard that may be due to different male to female proportion in sample size and ethnicity difference in various studies. In our study no significant difference of histological

grading of tumor found according to various age groups, while few studies reported high grade malignancy in old age people.^{13,20,21} Urothelial carcinoma of urinary bladder is the 4th commonest tumor among males and 9th commonest tumor among females in USA. It is associated with high morbidity and mortality. It contributes 93.4% of all urinary bladder malignancies. In 75%-85% cases it is limited to the mucosa and don't progress further and recurrence rate is high after local resection. In our study proportion of females having carcinoma was lower than males but disease progression was more than males. Similar results were reported by Sikic D et al. [21,22] Difference in androgen and estrogen receptors expression of tumor cells can explain gender specificity of the tumor.

CONCLUSION:

Males are more commonly affected with urothelial carcinoma than females but disease progression is more among females. No significant age correlation of tumor found. Smoking is a major risk factor of carcinoma. Further study is required in which smoking and menopausal risk factors should be excluded to assess gender association of the tumor.

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